

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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HEALING PROPERTIES OF ALOE PLANT

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Abstract: This article provides interesting information about the Aloe plant and the current medicinal properties of the Aloe plant and its preparations.

Keywords: Bacteriocidal properties of immunity, eye diseases, gynecological diseases, components, beta-carotene, acids lemon, apple, hyaluronic, minerals phosphorus, calcium, potassium, zinc, chromium, copper, carbohydrates glucose, fructose, cellulose, essential oils, Vitamins C, E, B group.

It is known that Aloe is a very useful plant. It is an effective tool in preventing various diseases in the body. However, many consider this plant as an ordinary houseplant. In fact, the properties of aloe in medicine are very great. For example, aloe contains a substance that prevents the growth of bacteria. That's why aloe leaf is split lengthwise in the middle and bandaged by placing it on the painful area so that it does not fester when a bee bites its leaf, cuts the skin with a knife or something else. Aqueous extract of aloe has immunostimulating properties and protects the body from various diseases.

Aloe juice contains beta-carotene, acids (lemon, apple, hyaluronic), minerals (phosphorus, calcium, potassium, zinc, chromium, copper), carbohydrates (glucose, fructose, cellulose), essential oils, C, E, B group vitamins formed. Also, in medicine, this plant is used as an expectorant, laxative, medicine, and wound healing agent. Eye drops containing aloe effectively help in conjunctivitis, blepharitis, myopia, keratitis. It is recommended to rinse the mouth in case of inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity. Aloe extract is considered a unique component and is used in the food industry for the production of yogurts, sweets and drinks. High aloe extract has antioxidant, antibacterial, restorative and antiallergic properties. Aloe extract cleans the lymph, improves blood circulation, and also accelerates the transport of oxygen to the organs, which has a positive effect on the health of the heart and brain. In cosmetology, it is used to soften and rejuvenate the skin, moisturize the skin, fight against signs of aging, and remove wrinkles. Wound treatment - promotes rapid healing of superficial wounds and deep wounds,

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accelerates epithelization and synthesis of fibroblasts. Antiseptic - fights bacterial and viral infections, acne and inflammatory reactions. Soothing - helps with burns and frostbite, eliminates symptoms such as itching, irritation, redness and peeling.

Lightening - works against excessive skin pigmentation, brightens existing spots and prevents the appearance of new ones.

The uniqueness of this plant lies in its various biological activities: from healing wounds to fighting bacteria. It is known that the plant is as safe as possible and is even suitable for people with sensitive skin, as well as those who are prone to allergies. Flavonoids in the plant are substances with an antioxidant effect. They prevent inflammation and heal wounds. Aloe has an anti-aging effect and prevents the decrease in collagen and elastin synthesis caused by the negative effects of external factors. In addition, aloe stimulates hair growth and restores its structure. It is used in the treatment of respiratory diseases, for example: tuberculosis, angina, cough, flu, bronchial asthma, pneumonia, pulmonary tuberculosis. In stomatology, aloe is also used when the gums are inflamed and painful. There are more than 250 species of aloe grown as annual plants in Central Asia, 15 of which are medicinal. 4 types of aloe are used to obtain medicinal raw materials. These are aloe vera (aloe barbaodensis), aloe tree (aloe arborescens) aloe socotrinskoe (aloe succotrena) and amazing aloe (aloe freaks). Summing up this article, it can be said that aloe is primarily an ornamental and medicinal plant. There are many types of aloe and all of them are medicinal. It is necessary to learn the correct use of the medicinal properties of these plants, to extract the substances contained in them in a pure form, and to prepare medicinal preparations from them and use them in folk medicine and medicine. Side effects are very few. Severe diseases; it cannot be used in acute type of gastrointestinal diseases, liver diseases.

The demand for aloe plant and its preparations abroad is much higher than in our country. We need to grow and use wisely such a plant rich in useful content. We need to grow special plantations to grow this plant.

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